

Neighbourhood vitality and physical activity among the elderly: The role of walkable environments on active ageing in Barcelona, Spain

Abstract: This study investigated whether neighbourhood vitality and walkability were associated with active ageing of the elderly. Immobility, activity engagement and physical activity were explored in relation with age, gender and walkability of the built environment. Number of trips per day and minutes spent on walking by the elderly were extracted from a broad travel survey with more than 12,000 CATI interviews and were compared across vital and non-vital urban environments. Results highlight the importance of vital environments for elderly active mobility as subpopulations residing in highly walkable neighbourhoods undertook more trips and spent more minutes walking than their counterparts. The results also suggest that the built environment has different effects in terms of gender, as elderly men were more susceptible to urban vitality than elderly women.

Keywords: Spain; Active ageing; physical activity; active mobility; neighborhood vitality

1. Background

Like many European Countries, Spain faces the challenge of a rapidly ageing population. Having an old age dependency ratio of 26.3, the pace of ageing is much higher in Spain than in other countries, and it is projected that by the year 2050 its old age dependency ratio will be 26% higher than that of the EU28 (EUROSTAT, 2014). Barcelona's Metropolitan Region is no exception to that general dynamic and in 2013 it had 17.4% of its population older than 65 years, with an elder-child ratio of 107 (IDESCAT, 2013). Within the next 15 years, 22% of the population will be above 65 years of age and the elder-child ratio will be 147. The increase of the senior population, not only in Spain but all over Europe, has focused public health policies on the need to promote healthier mobility habits in favour of physical activity (PA) and activity engagement.

PA directly affects several health issues in the general population, all of which become more urgent in the age range of the elderly. The World Health Organization (WHO) identifies the lack of PA as the fourth global risk factor, globally accounting for 6% of deaths (WHO, 2010). In general terms, more active individuals have lower mortality rates, in comparison with people who remain sedentary (Gregg et al., 2003; Stessman et al., 2009). Other demonstrated effects of the lack of PA are cardiovascular diseases, some types of cancer, arthritis and obesity (Ewing et al., 2014; Jongeneel-Grimen et al., 2014). According to the current recommendations, seniors should perform moderate-intensity PA, for at least 150 minutes throughout the week, which can be the result of adding shorter PA bouts (WHO, 2010). Over the past few years, there has been a great increase of studies linking PA with general health status (Ewing et al., 2014; Ewing et al., 2008; Jongeneel-Grimen et al., 2014), and specifically with elderly mobility (Moniruzzaman et al., 2013; Páez et al., 2007; Hildebrand, 2003).

In terms of transportation, walking has been seen as the key for resolving most elderly problems related with PA. Walking for transport is a major source of physical activity, especially for people over 65 years of age who perceive the options for using other types of transport as being reduced (Balboa-Castillo et al., 2011). Walking is seen as a convenient, safe and adequate activity for seniors as it places the right amount of stress on joints in the human body (Moniruzzaman et al., 2013). The recognition of walking as a means of transport and as a source of moderate PA has led urban planners to focus on creating walkable environments that make active mobility more appealing (Clarke & Nieuwenhuijsen, 2009; Handy & Boarnet, 2002; Lamíquiz & López-Domínguez, 2015; Talavera-Garcia & Soria-Lara, 2015).

Furthermore, urban settings not only determine PA but also psychological wellbeing and mental health (Fujiwara & Kawachi, 2008; Clark et al., 2007). Studies have demonstrated how mental health depends heavily on social capital (Bowling & Stafford, 2007) and resources that individuals can access through their networks (Fujiwara & Kawachi, 2008). For individuals above the age of 65 years, living in a vital and thriving urban environment may mean undertaking more trips, engaging in more activities (Hildebrand, 2003) and interacting with more people in their everyday life (Kuo et al., 1998; Kweon et al., 1998). All of the aforementioned contributes to increasing their social capital status while avoiding social exclusion processes derived from immobility (Hanibuchi et al., 2012; Richard et al., 2009; Leyden, 2003). The relation between built environment attributes and mental health condition is thus recognised through the number of activities which the elderly can perform within a walking distance.

Currently, there is enough empirical evidence to corroborate that the way neighbourhoods are designed influences walking behaviour (Villanueva et al., 2014). At

an age where adults experience a reduction in functional capacities, the settings of the built environment become even more important, as they have the potential to either compensate the deficits in mobility capacity or to exacerbate mobility problems (Dujardin et al., 2014).

There are few articles that try to assess both the physical and mental health of the elderly through their use of active mobility. Most of the research is focused either on PA of seniors (Kerr et al., 2012; Lockett et al., 2005; Michael et al., 2014; Michael et al., 2006; Michael et al., 2010) or on the social capital status of seniors (Bowling & Stafford, 2007; Fujiwara & Kawachi, 2008; Hanibuchi et al., 2012; Leyden, 2003; Richard et al., 2009), without always realising that neighbourhood settings have the potential to determine both the modal choice of the trip (and thus the PA) and the number of trips that the elderly undertake, which relates with activity engagement. Furthermore, and as Sugiyama et al. (2014) suggest, limited variation in environmental attributes may be causing most non-significant or weak associations between neighbourhood environmental attributes with physical activity.

Hence, we believe that the analysis of how the built environment determines the health of seniors, through promoting active mobility, is far from being closed. Our study aims to understand how living in vital or non-vital urban areas can change the travel behaviour of the elderly along with the amount of PA that they are gaining from walking for transport.

Our view of urban vitality takes the seminal works of the American city activist, Jane Jacobs (1961), who measured the vitality of an urban area by using the walking activity on the streets as a reference. For Jacobs, the vitality of the streets was a product of the diversity of the built environment, and the presence of pedestrians served as an indicator of the city liveliness (Sung et al., 2013). We thus understand urban vitality as a

synonym of vibrant environments and we measure this vitality, not from a set of morphological indicators (Aditjandra et al., 2012) nor as a personal well-being indicator (Guite et al., 2006; Richard et al., 2009), but through the observation of mobility patterns. Those areas where a large part of daily mobility is performed through short walking trips are labelled as vital areas. The presence of short walking trips characterises not only areas with a high intensity of pedestrians, but also by their proximity to services, amenities, and land use mix (Marquet & Miralles-Guasch, 2015; Morency, Paez, Roorda, Mercado, & Farber, 2011), forming a particularly suitable urban environment for ageing populations (Marquet & Miralles-Guasch, 2014) and shaping what American urban planner Kevin Lynch understood was a place that supported the biological requirements and capabilities of human beings (Lynch, 1981, p. 118). Having pedestrians on the street increases the appeal of walking (Gehl, 2010) and the potential enjoyment of the trip (Gehl, 2011, p. 68), also making walking more attractive for the elderly. In contrast, areas where short walking trips are scarce often represent low-density built environments that offer neither proximate facilities nor vibrant street life for elderly walkers.

Comparing the health outputs of the elderly populations living in vital or non-vital areas can provide an idea of how much healthy mobility habits can be improved by investing in vital built environments.

2. Sources and Methodology

In order to understand the determinants of physical activity and activity engagement for the ageing population, we need information sources where all types of daily trips are treated in the same way. Daily travel surveys, such as the one used for the present study are useful because of their homogeneous treatment, including all types of

means of transport, trip purposes and journey durations. In this methodological section we intend to address both data sources and the reasons for choosing our population and territorial variables along with the methods of analysis.

2.1 Data Sources and measures

The study took place in Barcelona's Metropolitan Region (RMB), a 3,200 km² metropolitan area located north-east of Spain, made up of 164 municipalities that gather a total of 4,635,5421 inhabitants. The region is strongly centralised within the Barcelona environment, but it gets polycentric, discontinuous and disperse as one moves away from the core of Barcelona (Muñiz & Galindo, 2005).

The main data source is a broad travel survey, Everyday Mobility Inquiry (ATM and GC 2006), that was performed in 2006 (hereafter, EMQ06) by the regional authorities in Catalonia (Spain). It aims to describe the mobility of the resident population of Catalonia with 106,091 Computer Assisted Telephone Interviews (CATI), out of which 45,184 were located in our area of study, Barcelona Metropolitan Region (RMB). The interviews were used to gather data regarding trips taken in a working day and also included some socioeconomic input about the interviewee.

Mobility data and variables, such as number of trips, modal choice, travel duration or physical activity related to transport per person were extracted from the EMQ06. However, other sources were needed to gather socioeconomic variables at the neighbourhood level, such as income or motorisation levels, and territorial variables like population density or land use distribution. Socioeconomic data were extracted from the official Statistics Institute of Catalonia (IDESCAT) and the official Statistics Service of Barcelona.

Our focus was set on the health-related aspects of travelling for the elderly population, particularly on the rates of change of healthy mobility habits that can be gained from moving from a non-vital area to a vital area. The study represents the built environment on its most local scale, which is consistent with the analysis of a population with low mobility potential (Prins et al., 2014). Health outcome variables are divided into activity engagement measures and physical activity measures. Firstly, immobility is a dichotomous proxy for activity engagement. In that, following a fairly common definition of immobility (Sikder & Pinjari, 2012), when a person claims not to have left the house the day prior to the interview, we consider it a case of immobility. Secondly, activity engagement is a continuous variable: number of trips made on the day prior to the interview. This variable provides the average number of trips in terms of age, gender and urban vitality. PA measures are expressed through two variables: modal choice and number of minutes spent on walking. All the results were stratified by gender (male/female), age (64-75 and >75 years) and urban vitality (vital or non-vital).

2.2 Study areas and population sample

Our target of study was that of the census population of citizens over 65 years of age. This large group was divided into two subgroups, consisting of Seniors (65-74 years of age) and Elderly Seniors (75 years of age and older). This distinction was necessary as travel behaviour changes with respect to the physical possibilities and moving capacities of the studied population (Kerr et al., 2012). Gender was also taken into account as males and females show very different modal choices as well as different allocations of travel times and trip purposes (Hanson, 2010; Miralles-Guasch et al., 2015). Having divided the older population by age and gender, we were able to analyse how the territorial settings and vitality of their built environment determined

their travel behaviour and the total amount of physical activity they were gaining from transportation.

The neighbourhoods were sorted between vital and non-vital areas, vitality being measured through the frequency on which the general population of each study area were taking short walking trips. We used a 10 minute threshold to define a short trip, a temporal measure consistently used in previous transport studies (Ryley, 2008; Li et al., 2005). The general assumption was that the way in which the residents of each area were moving was indicative of the physical settings and walkability of the area. Furthermore, we hypothesised that a neighbourhood that enabled short walking mobility for the general population would also be encouraging for the active mobility of the elderly (Moniruzzaman et al., 2013).

On average, people in the Barcelona Metropolitan Region were using short walking trips for 27% of their everyday trips (standard deviation=9.6). We decided to label those study areas that had a use of short walking trips above the 31.8% (+1/2 SD from the average) as vital areas. Those vital areas had 15% more population density than the average, with a building typology consistent with attached dwellings with abundant commercial facilities (see Table 1). Conversely, those areas with less than 22.2% (-1/2 SD) of short walking trips were labelled as non-vital ones. These non-vital zones had lower population density (18% less than the average), higher average incomes and a land-use distribution which is dominated by single dwellings.

Assuming an average walking speed of 4 km/h (Duffy & Crawford 2013; Ritsema van Eck et al., 2005) these 10-minutes-or-less walking trips cover a maximum topological distance of 650 m. This means that urban areas where a great part of the daily mobility is performed through those types of trips are vital areas where the optimum mix of population density, land use distribution, built environment design and

connectivity, are offering to its citizens the possibility to reach daily needs inside a proximate area (Marquet & Miralles-Guasch, 2015). The result of this procedure was the selection of the most- and least-walkable urban environments, by observing the travelling behaviour of the overall population, not just the seniors (see Table 1).

Table 1. Descriptive characteristics of vital and non-vital areas

	Vital areas	Non-Vital areas	Barcelona Metropolitan Region
Sample	<i>n (%)</i>	<i>n (%)</i>	<i>n (%)</i>
Male	1813 (15.2%)	898 (7.5%)	4937 (41.1%)
Female	2994 (20.8%)	1215 (10.1%)	7082 (58.9%)
Senior (65-74)	2394 (19.9%)	1042 (8.7%)	6283 (52.3%)
Elder senior (75+)	1923 (16%)	1071 (8.9%)	5736 (47.7%)
Socioeconomics	Mean (<i>IQR</i>)	Mean (<i>IQR</i>)	Mean (<i>IQR</i>)
Municipality size	17839.9 (9769)	10324.6 (10625)	15678.9 (14405)
Average income	12901.6 (1814)	15469.5 (4638)	14297.7 (5270)
Vehicle/1000 hab	568.1 (333)	728.0 (226)	638.9 (140)
Population density	2456.4 (754)	1737.3 (768)	2133.9 (875)
Land Use distribution	Mean (Std Dev)	Mean (Std Dev)	Mean (Std Dev)
Single dwellings	10.9% (12.3)	36.2% (26.6)	44.2% (24.1)
Attached dwellings	59.4% (18)	24.5% (21.5)	21.1% (21,6)
Industrial land	14.1% (11.9)	24.0% (18.3)	19.1% (15.2)
Business facilities	1.9% (1.7)	3.8% (4.8)	2.8% (3.3)
Commercial facilities	7.4% (2.9)	3.3% (2.7)	5.6% (3.2)
Services facilities	6.4% (4)	7.5% (5.4)	6.7% (4.7)
Rural areas	0.1% (0.1)	0.7% (2.2)	0.2% (1.2)
Total	100 (-)	100 (-)	100 (-)

Source: Own elaboration from EMQ06 and IDESCAT

Table 1. Descriptive characteristics of vital and non-vital areas

	Vital areas	Non-Vital areas	Barcelona Metropolitan Region
Sample	<i>n</i> (%)	<i>n</i> (%)	<i>n</i> (%)
Male	1813 (15.2%)	898 (7.5%)	4937 (41.1%)
Female	2994 (20.8%)	1215 (10.1%)	7082 (58.9%)
Senior (65-74)	2394 (19.9%)	1042 (8.7%)	6283 (52.3%)
Elder senior (75+)	1923 (16%)	1071 (8.9%)	5736 (47.7%)
Socioeconomics	Mean (<i>IQR</i>)	Mean (<i>IQR</i>)	Mean (<i>IQR</i>)
Municipality size	17839.9 (9769)	10324.6 (10625)	15678.9 (14405)
Average income	12901.6 (1814)	15469.5 (4638)	14297.7 (5270)
Vehicle/1000 hab	568.1 (333)	728.0 (226)	638.9 (140)
Population density	2456.4 (754)	1737.3 (768)	2133.9 (875)
Land Use distribution	Mean (Std Dev)	Mean (Std Dev)	Mean (Std Dev)
Single dwellings	10.9% (12.3)	36.2% (26.6)	44.2% (24.1)
Attached dwellings	59.4% (18)	24.5% (21.5)	21.1% (21,6)
Industrial land	14.1% (11.9)	24.0% (18.3)	19.1% (15.2)
Business facilities	1.9% (1.7)	3.8% (4.8)	2.8% (3.3)
Commercial facilities	7.4% (2.9)	3.3% (2.7)	5.6% (3.2)
Services facilities	6.4% (4)	7.5% (5.4)	6.7% (4.7)
Rural areas	0.1% (0.1)	0.7% (2.2)	0.2% (1.2)
Total	100 (-)	100 (-)	100 (-)

Source: Own elaboration from EMQ06 and IDESCAT

3. Results

3.1 Trip frequency and activity engagement

The first measure of activity engagement has to be whether the person is mobile or immobile. Immobility is a major concern in ageing populations, when the natural decrease of personal physical capabilities forces the person to stay at home. The immobile person becomes dependant on others to fulfil their daily needs and this also prevents the person from fully participating in community life, increasing the chances of starting a process that moves towards social disadvantage or even social exclusion.

Of the total of 738,064 people older than 65 years of age and living in the metropolitan area, 114,399 (15.5%) declared not having made a single trip on the surveyed working day (see Table 2), when the general immobility ratio for the metropolitan region is set at 6.2%. Logically, this figure is strongly determined by age, because the immobility rate more than doubles itself as the 75 years old threshold (from 10.4% to 21.2%) is approached. Almost the same differences can be spotted in terms of gender, with 19.6% of females suffering from immobility against 9.6% of men.

The importance of the vitality of the area was also found significant, with a positive correlation between urban vitality and immobility ($r=0.043$, $p<0.001$). Areas with higher vitality have less immobility in every age and gender category. Also, the figures for the non-vital areas are found to be significantly higher in all but one category. The impact of living in vital or non-vital areas is strongest on the elderly seniors, where it can pose a change of 18% in the number of immobile individuals. The most important differences are found in the case of male elderly seniors where nearly 20% of those who live in non-vital areas are immobile, compared with 13% of those living in vital areas. Furthermore, the population subgroup where immobility is more frequent is that of female elderly seniors, where more than a quarter of the population (25.5%) are not taking a single trip. In this group, the vitality of the neighbourhood is found to be significant at explaining lower values of immobility (23.4%).

Table 2. Percentage of non-mobile population by gender age and area type

Gender	Age group	Area type (%)		Total	Ratio (a/b)
		Vital (a)	Non-Vital (b)		
Men	Senior 65-74	6.5	8.2	6.8	0.793
	Elder Senior >75	13.4	19.7	13.5	0.680
	Total	9.1	13.3	9.6	0.684
Women	Senior 65-74	13.8	13.8	13.3	1
	Elder Senior >75	23.4	25.6	25.5	0.914

	Total	18.5	20.3	19.6	0.911
	Senior 65-74	10.4	11.1	10.4	0.937
Total	Elder Senior >75	19.8	23.4	21.2	0.846
	Total	14.6	17.3	15.5	0.844
Population		277,954	136,047	414,001	

Source: own elaboration from EMQ06

Test: Chi² sig=000 all categories; Adjusted residuals test, corrected.

In gray shading: significantly higher values

Bold: significantly lower values

** Non-significant data, insufficient sample frequency per cell

The relation between age and number of trips is significant ($\chi^2=464.5$ $p<0.001$), as well as the relation between gender and number of trips ($\chi^2=379.8$ $p<0.001$). After these two main relations, the settings of the built environment are also found to be significant ($\chi^2=56.320$ $p<0.001$). As shown in Table 3, the average senior on the metropolitan region undertakes 2.99 trips a day, but gender, age and location determine the exact rate of daily trips made by each population subgroup. As a constant, in vital neighbourhoods, people are taking more trips than in other areas. This increase does not change significantly in terms of age, as the differences are very similar when we compare Seniors (1.066 ratio) and Elderly Seniors (1.064 ratio). The significant differences are found for the gender variable. In general, women with more than 65 years of age take 21% less trips than men of the same age, but where a Senior male (65-74 years of age) is making 3.69 trips a day, a Senior female is making only 3.08 trips a day. The same trend is reproduced on the Elderly Senior category (3.02 vs. 2.33, respectively). Even more relevant, the number of total trips taken by Males is more affected by the vitality of the neighbourhood than those taken by women. Men living in a vital and proximate neighbourhood are taking 11.3% more trips than men who live in non-vital areas (1.127 ratio). In contrast, the trip rates for women are steady despite the territorial settings, and living in a vital area entails only making 4.1% more trips than those people who live in non-vital areas.

Table 3. Number of trips by gender age and area type

Gender	Age group	Area type		Total	Ratio (a/b)
		Vital (a)	Non-Vital (b)		
Men	Senior 65-74	3.84	3.46	3.69	1.110
	Elder Senior >75	3.12	2.79	3.02	1.118
	Total	3.56	3.16	3.41	1.127
Women	Senior 65-74	3.04	2.96	3.08	1.027
	Elder Senior >75	2.40	2.32	2.33	1.034
	Total	2.72	2.61	2.70	1.042
Total	Senior 65-74	3.41	3.20	3.36	1.066
	Elder Senior >75	2.66	2.50	2.58	1.064
	Total	3.08	2.97	2.99	1.037

Source: own elaboration from EMQ06

Test: Chi² sig=000 all categories; Adjusted residuals test, corrected.

** Non-significant data, insufficient sample frequency per cell

3.2 Walking as a mode choice

Living in a vital or non-vital area has profound implications on transport behaviour in general, and particularly on modal choice. Table 4 shows the relationship between the characteristics of the urban area where seniors are living and the use of walking, public transport and private transport, with data being stratified by gender ($p < 0.001$). Overall, the senior population in the RMB is walking for transport for nearly 7 out of 10 journeys (69.8%) ($\chi^2=741.916$ $p<001$). Public transport is used on 17.3% of occasions, leaving private transport to account for 12.9% of trips. The vitality of the urban area appears to be just as relevant in determining all three travel modes. Its effects on walking are particularly strong, as those who live in vital areas are compelled to walk for 76.7% of their trips, 6.9 points higher than the total average. Their counterparts living in non-vital areas are using walking for transportation on only 56.8% of their trips, which means 13 points less than the total average. Also found to be significant, is the utilisation of public and private transport. The use of these means of transport is

constantly higher on non-vital areas, to a degree that varies from 13 to 18 percentage points from the total average. The characteristics of the urban area where the trip does take place have nearly identical effects, for either men or women. However, the same gendered differences that can be found throughout other ages are also reproduced in seniors, as men are using private transport more often than women, whether they live in vital or non-vital areas. These gendered differences are slightly stronger in non-vital areas, where women report walking 2 percentage points less than men, but are using private transport 10.2 points less. Also, the effect of the urban environment is stronger in women ($\chi^2=432.127$ $p<0.001$) than in men ($\chi^2=330.127$ $p<0.001$).

Table 4. Modal choice by gender and municipality type

Gender	Age group	Area type (%)		Total	Ratio (a/b)
		Vital (a)	Non Vital (b)		
Men	Walking	75.2	55.8	67.9	1.348
	Public Transport	10.8	18.5	14.5	0.584
	Private transport	14.0	25.7	17.6	0.545
	Total	100	100	100	1
Women	Walking	78.1	57.8	71.5	1.351
	Public Transport	15.2	26.7	19.8	0.569
	Private transport	6.6	15.5	8.8	0.426
	Total	100	100	100	1
Total	Walking	76.7	56.8	69.8	1.350
	Public Transport	13.1	22.8	17.3	0.575
	Private transport	10.2	20.3	12.9	0.502
	Total	100	100	100	1

Source: own elaboration from EMQ06

Test: Chi² sig=000 all categories; Adjusted residuals test, corrected.

In gray shading: significantly higher values

Bold: significantly lower values

** Non-significant data, insufficient sample frequency per cell

3.3 Physical Activity and WHO recommendations

It is through this increased ratio of walking journeys, that the urban environment expresses its effect on the overall physical activity of the resident senior population. We have seen how seniors choose to walk for transport more often in vital areas. But, how does this correlate with the actual minutes spent on walking and by extension on their physical activity?

Our main hypothesis was that, living in a vital or non-vital environment created a significant difference, not only on the number of walking trips, but also on the number of minutes invested in walking for transport. In order to test the hypothesis, an independent samples t-test was performed, the results of which were the realisation that the relationship actually existed between variables ($t=69.12$; $p<0.001$). Numerically, this relationship can be seen in Table 5. The general trend, as also noted for the number of trips, is that men walk more minutes than women (86.6 vs. 57.7, respectively), and that seniors also do so in comparison with elder seniors (76.4 vs. 63.0, respectively).

Overall, living in a vital environment is equivalent to walking 4.8 more minutes than living in a non-vital environment.. Differences, however, are particularly gendered, as the physical activity of men appears to be highly dependent of the vitality of the neighbourhood. For male Seniors (65-74 years of age) the differences can be up to 16 minutes less a day, although these differences are attenuated on the male Elderly Seniors (>75 years of age) for which there is only a 3 minute difference between vital and non-vital neighbourhoods. In contrast, women appear to draw contradictory results.

Table 5. Average minutes spend on walking by gender, age and area type

Gender	Age group	Area type			
		Vital (a) (Minutes)	Non Vital (b) (Minutes)	Total (Minutes)	Differences (a-b) (Minutes)
	Senior 65-74	102.0	86.2	94.0	+15.8
Men	Elder Senior >75	74.9	71.8	76.4	+3.1
	Total	91.6	80.3	86.6	+11.3

	Senior 65-74	61.1	55.5	61.0	+5.6
Women	Elder Senior >75	51.1	57.6	54.2	-6.5
	Total	56.6	56.6	57.7	0
	Senior 65-74	80.8	71.3	76.4	+9.5
Total	Elder Senior >75	60.7	63.0	63.0	-2.3
	Total	72.1	67.3	70.3	+4.8
	Population	277,954	136,047	414,001	

Source: own elaboration from EMQ06

Test: Chi² sig=000 all categories; Adjusted residuals test, corrected.

** Non-significant data, insufficient sample frequency per cell

Following the established link between physical activity, urban vitality and walking for transport, one can relate the characteristics of the neighbourhood with how people perform, in accordance with the WHO physical activity standards. In Table 6, we demonstrate how the different sample subgroups get to the recommended threshold of 30 minutes walked per day, which would correspond to 30 minutes of moderate physical activity. As expected, there is a strong statistical significance between achieving the recommended amount of daily physical activity and the area vitality ($\chi^2=2005.977$ $p<0.001$). Numerically, these differences mean that in all the sample groups, those who lived in vital areas were more prone to achieving the recommendations than their counterparts living in non-vital areas. The higher differences can be found in Males, for whom the area vitality can mean a 35.4% difference. Female differences are lower (25.1%), but they consistently fail to achieve the WHO minimums as, even in vital urban areas, only 37.4% of them are walking more than 30 minutes every day.

Table 6. Percentage of population over 30 min walking by gender, age and area type

Gender	Age group	Area type (%)			Ratio (a/b)
		Vital (a)	Non Vital (b)	Total	
Men	Senior 65-74	58.4	43.6	51.7	1.339

	Elder Senior >75	48.7	36.4	48.3	1.338
	Total	54.7	40.4	49.3	1.354
<hr/>					
	Senior 65-74	41.1	28.2	39.5	1.457
Women	Elder Senior >75	33.7	31.2	33.6	1.080
	Total	37.4	29.9	35.6	1.251
<hr/>					
	Senior 65-74	49.2	35.6	43.6	1.382
Total	Elder Senior >75	39.1	33.1	38.8	1.181
	Total	44.7	34.3	41.3	1.303
<hr/>					
	Population	277,954	136,047	414,001	

Source: own elaboration from EMQ06

Test: Chi² sig=.000 all categories; Adjusted residuals test, corrected.

In gray shading: significantly higher values

Bold: significantly lower values

** Non-significant data, insufficient sample frequency per cell

4. Discussion

This study explored whether urban vitality is associated with PA and activity engagement of the elderly. We found that the elderly living in thriving areas are less immobile, take more trips per day, choose walking as a means of transport more often and also walk for more minutes than those who live in non-vital areas.

In contrast with the results of Forsyth et al. (2009), our results clearly demonstrate how the environment has different effects on different social groups, especially in terms of age and gender. The general trend is that the role of the built environment in modifying PA and travel behaviour is exacerbated as age grows, but most importantly, we found that the results were also gender related, as men were more affected by the settings of the built environment than women. The importance of the gender variable among elderly PA remains heavily understudied. Only some studies, such as those by Bauer et al. (2003) and Gregg et al. (2003) examined the specific travel patterns of older women, although not specifically the gender differences with men. In

contrast, Hakamies-Blomqvist & Siren (2003) did indeed examine gender differences, but only focused on the driving cessation issue.

The results of this study have demonstrated that the lack of urban vitality is consistently found as significant to explain higher immobility cases in the elderly of all ages and gender (see Table 2). Also noteworthy, results have shown that urban vitality does not always mean a low immobility ratio, as there are several other factors at play. As Schwanen & Paez (2010) suggest, the reduction and cessation of driving, as a result of a decrease on the corporeal capacities, has a significant impact on mobility patterns of elderly (Harrison & Ragland, 2003), especially when a non-walkable urban environment offers no alternatives. In the Barcelona Metropolitan Region 49.8% of people between 65-74 years of age still have a driving licence, whereas only 25% of people older than 75 years of age still have one. Besides being a symbol of becoming old, not being able to drive makes elderly become increasingly dependent on the potential of their neighbourhood. That is why the differences between immobility in vital and non-vital environments are exacerbated above the age of 75 years, when car use drops due to age. Our results suggest that immobility numerically affects women more than men, but at the same time reveal that men are more subject to the characteristics of the built environment. These may be in line with the findings of Bauer et al. (2003), as women, who have lived with lower motorisation rates than men, tend to adapt better to life after the car, and are less dependent on the potential of their built environment. Overall, the loss of mobility capacities entails a loss of control over their own lives along with a fear of becoming a burden to families and with losing social capital.

This study has also found that seniors living in vital urban areas are making more trips than those who live in non-vital ones, which means that they are also

engaging in more activities (see Table 3). Hence, it can be stated that living in vital urban areas is helping their mental health, as performing more activities has been positively associated by Putnam (2000, p. 328) and Pollack & Knesebeck (2004) with general health and wellbeing. Results also show that trip frequency decreases with age, both in vital and non-vital areas, as men and women equally reported a drop in their daily trips as they grew older. This findings are in line with those by Giuliano (1999) and, more recently, by Paez et al. (2007) and Petterson and Shmoker (2010). Our results, however, go further and suggest that elderly women take fewer trips than elderly men and also, most importantly, that as in the case of immobility, living in a vital or non-vital area also had a greater effect on trip frequency for men than for women.

The degree upon which these trips are converted onto PA depends on how often the elderly are choosing walking as a means of transport. Walking is 20% more frequent in vital areas than in non-vital areas, which effectively links neighbourhood walkability with actually walking for transport (see Table 4). In all the comparisons between identical seniors (same age and same gender) those who live in vital neighbourhoods report walking more often than those who live in non-walkable neighbourhoods. This is fully consistent with what Villanueva et al. (2014) and McCormack et al. (2014) have recently found in population subgroups of all ages and also what King et al. (2011) found, specifically on population groups above the age of 65 years. This preference for walking in vital environments makes residents in these areas report nearly 5 more minutes of PA every day. In terms of weekly PA, there is a 34-minute difference between residents of vital and non-vital areas, which locates our results on the higher range of the 22-40 minute span reported by King et al. (2011).

Overall, 41.3% of the elderly in the Barcelona Metropolitan Region reach the WHO recommended 30 minutes of PA per day. This figure is far better than the one

found by Pucher et al. (2011) with respect to the US and also higher than the 28.2% found by Buehler et al. (2011) with respect to Germany. Living in a vital urban environment improves the chances of reaching the WHO threshold, as 44.7% of the seniors inhabiting these areas walk for more than 30 minutes per day. The fact that urban vitality positively affects PA in all gender and age combinations is encouraging, towards designing public health interventions through urban policy, as actions taken in the urban environment positively affect all mobility habits of the elderly.

Taken globally, these results suggest that the hypothesis upon which urban vitality entails higher physical activity and activity engagement can be fully sustained. Furthermore, these results confirm the hypothesis that living in vital urban environments contributes to building healthy mobility habits, as the proximity to facilities and having people walking on the street encourages the elderly to make more trips which involve walking more often. Finally, it is also interesting to note how gender accounts for more differences than age itself, when most of the literature focuses on the ageing process as the main game changer for elderly mobility. The specific findings on how urban vitality and the settings of the built environment have different effects on men and women, opens future lines of research and may lead to recommending integrating gender on studies of the elderly on a regular basis.

5. References

- Aditjandra, P., Cao, X., & Mulley, C. (2012). Understanding neighbourhood design impact on travel behaviour: An application of structural equations model to a British metropolitan data. *Transportation Research Part A: Policy and Practice*, *46*, 22–32. Retrieved from <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0965856411001340>
- Balboa-Castillo, T., Guallar-Castillón, P., León-Muñoz, L. M., Graciani, A., López-García, E., & Rodríguez-Artalejo, F. (2011). Physical activity and mortality related to obesity and functional status in older adults in Spain. *American Journal of Preventive Medicine*, *40*(1), 39–46. doi:10.1016/j.amepre.2010.10.005
- Bauer, M. J., Rottunda, S., & Adler, G. (2003). Older Women and Driving Cessation. *Qualitative Social Work*, *2*(3), 309–325. doi:10.1177/14733250030023006
- Bowling, A., & Stafford, M. (2007). How do objective and subjective assessments of neighbourhood influence social and physical functioning in older age? Findings from a British survey of ageing. *Social Science & Medicine*, *64*, 2533–2549. doi:10.1016/j.socscimed.2007.03.009
- Buehler, R., Pucher, J., Merom, D., & Bauman, A. (2011). Active travel in Germany and the U.S. Contributions of daily walking and cycling to physical activity. *American Journal of Preventive Medicine*, *41*(3), 241–50. doi:10.1016/j.amepre.2011.04.012
- Clark, C., Candy, B., & Stansfeld, S. (2007). A systematic review on the effect of the built and physical environment on mental health. *Journal of Public Mental Health*, *6*(2), 14–27.
- Clarke, P., & Nieuwenhuijsen, E. R. (2009). Environments for healthy ageing: A critical review. *Maturitas*, *64*(1), 14–19. Retrieved from <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0378512209002576>
- Duffy, A., & Crawford, R. (2013). The effects of physical activity on greenhouse gas emissions for common transport modes in European countries. *Transportation Research Part D: Transport and Environment*, *19*(0), 13–19. doi:10.1016/j.trd.2012.09.005
- Dujardin, C., Lorant, V., & Thomas, I. (2014). Self-assessed health of elderly people in Brussels: does the built environment matter? *Health & Place*, *27*, 59–67. doi:10.1016/j.healthplace.2014.01.003
- Ewing, R., Meakins, G., Hamidi, S., & Nelson, A. C. (2014). Relationship between urban sprawl and physical activity, obesity, and morbidity - update and refinement. *Health & Place*, *26*, 118–26. doi:10.1016/j.healthplace.2013.12.008

- Ewing, R., Schmid, T., Killingsworth, R., Zlot, A., & Raudenbush, S. (2008). Relationship between urban sprawl and physical activity, obesity, and morbidity. *American Journal of Health Promotion : AJHP*, *18*(1), 47–57. Retrieved from <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/13677962>
- Forsyth, A., Michael Oakes, J., Lee, B., & Schmitz, K. H. (2009). The built environment, walking, and physical activity: Is the environment more important to some people than others? *Transportation Research Part D: Transport and Environment*, *14*(1), 42–49. doi:10.1016/j.trd.2008.10.003
- Fujiwara, T., & Kawachi, I. (2008). A prospective study of individual-level social capital and major depression in the United States. *Journal of Epidemiology and Community Health*, *62*(7), 627–33. doi:10.1136/jech.2007.064261
- Gehl, J. (2010). *Cities for people*. Washington D.C: Island Press.
- Gehl, J. (2011). *Life Between Buildings: Using Public Space*. Island Press.
- Giuliano, G. (1999). Land Use and Travel Patterns Among the Elderly. In *Transportation in an aging society: A decade of experience* (pp. 192–210). Washington D.C: Transportation Research Board.
- Gregg, E. W., Cauley, J. a, Stone, K., Thompson, T. J., Bauer, D. C., Cummings, S. R., & Ensrud, K. E. (2003). Relationship of changes in physical activity and mortality among older women. *Journal of the American Medical Association*, *289*(18), 2379–86. doi:10.1001/jama.289.18.2379
- Guite, H. F., Clark, C., & Ackrill, G. (2006). The impact of the physical and urban environment on mental well-being. *Public Health*, *120*(12), 1117–26. doi:10.1016/j.puhe.2006.10.005
- Hakamies-blomqvist, L., & Siren, A. (2003). Deconstructing a gender difference : Driving cessation and personal driving history of older women. *Journal of Safety Research*, *34*, 383–388. doi:10.1016/j.jsr.2003.09.008
- Handy, S., & Boarnet, M. (2002). How the built environment affects physical activity. *American Journal of Preventive Medicine*, *23*(2S), 64–74. Retrieved from [https://woc.uc.pt/fcdef/course/MLDLELDL/2008-2009/AJ PREV MED 2002-built env1.pdf](https://woc.uc.pt/fcdef/course/MLDLELDL/2008-2009/AJ%20PREV%20MED%202002-built%20env1.pdf)
- Hanibuchi, T., Kondo, K., Nakaya, T., Shirai, K., Hirai, H., & Kawachi, I. (2012). Does walkable mean sociable? Neighborhood determinants of social capital among older adults in Japan. *Health & Place*, *18*(2), 229–39. doi:10.1016/j.healthplace.2011.09.015
- Hanson, S. (2010). Gender and mobility: new approaches for informing sustainability. *Gender, Place & Culture*, *17*(1), 5–23. doi:10.1080/09663690903498225

- Harrison, A., & Ragland, D. R. (2003). Consequences of driving reduction or cessation for older adults. *Transportation Research Record*, (1843), 96–104. doi:10.3141/1843-12
- Hildebrand, E. D. (2003). Dimensions in elderly travel behaviour: A simplified activity-based model using lifestyle clusters. *Transportation*, 285–306.
- Jacobs, J. (1961). *The death and life of great American cities*. New York: Vintage Group.
- Jongeneel-Grimen, B., Droomers, M., van Oers, H. a M., Stronks, K., & Kunst, A. E. (2014). The relationship between physical activity and the living environment: a multi-level analyses focusing on changes over time in environmental factors. *Health & Place*, 26, 149–60. doi:10.1016/j.healthplace.2013.12.003
- Kerr, J., Rosenberg, D., & Frank, L. (2012). The Role of the Built Environment in Healthy Aging: Community Design, Physical Activity, and Health among Older Adults. *Journal of Planning Literature*, 27(1), 43–60. doi:10.1177/0885412211415283
- King, A. C., Sallis, J. F., Frank, L. D., Saelens, B. E., Cain, K., Conway, T. L., ... Kerr, J. (2011). Aging in neighborhoods differing in walkability and income: associations with physical activity and obesity in older adults. *Social Science & Medicine*, 73(10), 1525–33. doi:10.1016/j.socscimed.2011.08.032
- Kuo, F. E., Sullivan, W. C., & Coley, R. L. (1998). Fertile Ground for Community: Inner-City Neighborhood Common Spaces. *American Journal of Community Psychology*, 26(6), 823–851.
- Kweon, B.-S., Sullivan, W. C., & Wiley, a. R. (1998). Green Common Spaces and the Social Integration of Inner-City Older Adults. *Environment and Behavior*, 30(6), 832–858. doi:10.1177/001391659803000605
- Lamíquiz, P. J., & López-Domínguez, J. (2015). Effects of built environment on walking at the neighbourhood scale. A new role for street networks by modelling their configurational accessibility? *Transportation Research Part A: Policy and Practice*, 74, 148–163. doi:10.1016/j.tra.2015.02.003
- Leyden, K. M. (2003). Social Capital and the Built Environment : The Importance of Walkable Neighborhoods. *American Journal of Public Health*, 93(9), 1546–1551.
- Li, F., Fisher, K. J., Brownson, R. C., & Bosworth, M. (2005). Multilevel modelling of built environment characteristics related to neighbourhood walking activity in older adults. *Journal of Epidemiology and Community Health*, 59(7), 558–564. doi:10.1136/jech.2004.028399
- Lockett, D., Willis, A., & Edwards, N. (2005). Through Seniors' Eyes: An Exploratory Qualitative Study to Identify Environmental Barriers to and Facilitators of Walking. *Canadian Journal of Nursing Research*, 37(3), 48–65. Retrieved from

<http://www.ingentaconnect.com/content/mcgill/cjnr/2005/00000037/00000003/art0004>

- Lynch, K. (1981). *A Theory of Good City Form*. Cambridge: The MIT Press.
- Marquet, O., & Miralles-Guasch, C. (2014). Walking short distances. The socioeconomic drivers for the use of proximity in everyday mobility in Barcelona. *Transportation Research Part A: Policy and Practice*, 70, 210–222. doi:<http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.tra.2014.10.007>
- Marquet, O., & Miralles-Guasch, C. (2015). The Walkable city and the importance of the proximity environments for Barcelona's everyday mobility. *Cities*, 42, 258–266. doi:10.1016/j.cities.2014.10.012
- McCormack, G. R., Shiell, A., Doyle-Baker, P. K., Friedenreich, C. M., & Sandalack, B. a. (2014). Subpopulation differences in the association between neighborhood urban form and neighborhood-based physical activity. *Health & Place*, 28C, 109–115. doi:10.1016/j.healthplace.2014.04.001
- Michael, Y. L., Green, M. K., & Farquhar, S. A. (2006). Neighborhood design and active aging. *Health & Place*, 12(4), 734–740. Retrieved from <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1353829205000419>
- Michael, Y. L., Nagel, C. L., Gold, R., & Hillier, T. A. (2014). Does change in the neighborhood environment prevent obesity in older women? *Social Science & Medicine*, 102, 129–137. Retrieved from <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S027795361300659X>
- Michael, Y. L., Perdue, L. A., Orwoll, E. S., Stefanick, M. L., & Marshall, L. M. (2010). Physical activity resources and changes in walking in a cohort of older men. *American Journal of Public Health*, 100(4), 654–60. doi:10.2105/AJPH.2009.172031
- Miralles-Guasch, C., Martinez Melo, M., & Marquet, O. (2015). A gender analysis of everyday mobility in urban and rural territories: from challenges to sustainability. *Gender, Place & Culture*, 37–41. doi:10.1080/0966369X.2015.1013448
- Moniruzzaman, M., Páez, A., Nurul Habib, K. M., & Morency, C. (2013). Mode use and trip length of seniors in Montreal. *Journal of Transport Geography*, 30, 89–99. doi:10.1016/j.jtrangeo.2013.03.007
- Morency, C., Paez, A., Roorda, M. J., Mercado, R., & Farber, S. (2011). Distance traveled in three Canadian cities: Spatial analysis from the perspective of vulnerable population segments. *Journal of Transport Geography*, 19(1), 39–50. doi:10.1016/j.jtrangeo.2009.09.013
- Muñiz, I., & Galindo, A. (2005). Urban form and the ecological footprint of commuting. The case of Barcelona. *Ecological Economics*, 55, 499–514. Retrieved from <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0921800904004471>

- Páez, A., Scott, D., Potoglou, D., Kanaroglou, P., & Newbold, K. B. (2007). Elderly Mobility: Demographic and Spatial Analysis of Trip Making in the Hamilton CMA, Canada. *Urban Studies*, *44*(1), 123–146. doi:10.1080/00420980601023885
- Pollack, C. E., & von dem Knesebeck, O. (2004). Social capital and health among the aged: comparisons between the United States and Germany. *Health & Place*, *10*(4), 383–91. doi:10.1016/j.healthplace.2004.08.008
- Prins, R. G., Pierik, F., Etman, a, Sterkenburg, R. P., Kamphuis, C. B. M., & van Lenthe, F. J. (2014). How many walking and cycling trips made by elderly are beyond commonly used buffer sizes: results from a GPS study. *Health & Place*, *27*, 127–33. doi:10.1016/j.healthplace.2014.01.012
- Pucher, J., Buehler, R., Merom, D., & Bauman, A. (2011). Walking and cycling in the United States, 2001-2009: evidence from the National Household Travel Surveys. *American Journal of Public Health*, *101* Suppl , S310–7. doi:10.2105/AJPH.2010.300067
- Putnam, R. D. (2000). *Bowling Alone. The collapse and revival of american community*. New York: Simon and Schuster Paperbacks.
- Richard, L., Gauvin, L., Gosselin, C., & Laforest, S. (2009). Staying connected: neighbourhood correlates of social participation among older adults living in an urban environment in Montréal, Quebec. *Health Promotion International*, *24*(1), 46–57. doi:10.1093/heapro/dan039
- Ritsema van Eck, J., Burghouwt, G., & Dijst, M. (2005). Lifestyles, spatial configurations and quality of life in daily travel: an explorative simulation study. *Journal of Transport Geography*, *13*(2), 123–134. doi:10.1016/j.jtrangeo.2004.04.013
- Ryley, T. J. (2008). The propensity for motorists to walk for short trips: Evidence from West Edinburgh. *Transportation Research Part A: Policy and Practice*, *42*(4), 620–628. doi:10.1016/j.tra.2008.01.005
- Schwanen, T., & Páez, A. (2010). The mobility of older people – an introduction. *Journal of Transport Geography*, *18*(5), 591–595. doi:10.1016/j.jtrangeo.2010.06.001
- Sikder, S., & Pinjari, A. R. (2012). Immobility Levels and Mobility Preferences among Elderly in the United States: Evidence from the 2009 National Household Travel Survey (NHTS). In *Transportation Research Record* (Vol. 677). Washington D.C.
- Stessman, J., Hammerman-Rozenberg, R., Cohen, A., Ein-Mor, E., & Jacobs, J. M. (2009). Physical activity, function, and longevity among the very old. *Archives of Internal Medicine*, *169*(16), 1476–83. doi:10.1001/archinternmed.2009.248
- Sugiyama, T., Cerin, E., Owen, N., Oyeyemi, A. L., Conway, T. L., Van Dyck, D., ... Sallis, J. F. (2014). Perceived neighbourhood environmental attributes associated

with adults' recreational walking: IPEN Adult study in 12 countries. *Health & Place*, 28C, 22–30. doi:10.1016/j.healthplace.2014.03.003

Sung, H.-G., Go, D.-H., & Choi, C. G. (2013). Evidence of Jacobs's street life in the great Seoul city: Identifying the association of physical environment with walking activity on streets. *Cities*, 35, 164–173. Retrieved from <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0264275113001066>

Talavera-Garcia, R., & Soria-Lara, J. A. (2015). Q-PLOS , developing an alternative walking index . A method based on urban design quality. *Cities*, 45, 7–17. doi:10.1016/j.cities.2015.03.003

Villanueva, K., Knuiman, M., Nathan, A., Giles-Corti, B., Christian, H., Foster, S., & Bull, F. (2014). The impact of neighborhood walkability on walking: does it differ across adult life stage and does neighborhood buffer size matter? *Health & Place*, 25, 43–6. doi:10.1016/j.healthplace.2013.10.005

World Health Organization (WHO). (2010). *Global Recommendations on Physical Activity for Health*. Geneva. Retrieved from http://www.who.int/dietphysicalactivity/factsheet_recommendations/en/index.html.